

INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEE TRAINING ON INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE IN KAKAMEGA COUNTY GENERAL TEACHING AND REFERRAL HOSPITAL, KENYA

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Abstract: The aim of change management is maximization of benefits and organizational objectives in the meantime lowering the chances and possibilities of failure as change is being implemented. There are reports that have been made concerning inadequacies within the health systems however much provision of healthcare services is a devolved function. This study investigated the influence of employee training on institutional performance in Kakamega County General Teaching and Referral Hospital, Kenya. The study adopted exploratory design. The respondents constituted of 551 employees from the 6 department of the hospital. Stratified sampling technique was used to put the respondents into two categories to ensure that all the respondents are adequately represented. Purposive sampling was useful upon selection of the departmental respondents. The study sample size was made up of 232 respondents. The study used questionnaire to collect primary data. To obtain adequate content validity, the researcher adopted an expert judgmental method. The use of Cronbach's alpha coefficient helped in determining the reliability of the study. Analysis of the quantitative data was done through descriptive statistics. The quantitative data achieved by the survey was presented in the form of mean averages, frequencies, and percentages. The study found that employee training a significant influence on institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital. The study concluded that training improves performance by lowering employee turnover and raising commitment to organizational goals and objectives. The study recommended that the hospital should conduct a training needs assessment in order to establish a fundamental and distinct business goal for the training supports.

Keywords: Employee Training, Institutional Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

A variety of elements influence organizational change (Gwengi, 2018). In essence, organizational change management may be impacted by environmental changes. Additionally, businesses may need to identify the real causes of changing factors that have an impact on both the internal and external environment during times of crisis in order to decide which changes to make (Jones, 2014). According to George and Jones (2017), whenever an organization changes, the core values must be clearly stated in order to maintain the transformation process. The two authors also emphasized that even if an organization may undergo several organizational changes that are inconsistent, the nature of those changes is not always the same because change can occur in a variety of ways and can either be proactive or reactive.

Daniels (2013) highlights those internal processes in change management, such as employee training, enable employees to have the needed skills, information, and a clear understanding of the institution and its goals. Training of employees is also necessary for change management as it enables the employees to improve their effectiveness in the working environment

through modification of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Proctor and Doukakis (2016) highlight that employee training as an internal change management process enhances desired institutional performance and contributes to the institutional stability index. Therefore, employee training is a change management action needed to develop and improve institutional performance.

Performance of an institution is measured by establishing how effective and efficient an organization is and complying with the set rules and regulation. Institutional performance also includes measures in safeguarding and environmental conservation (Teeratansirikool, Siengthai, Badir & Charoenngam, 2013). Vanderstraeten and Matthyssens (2012) note that the performance of an institution as the indicator that brings out the relationship between the way in which firms deals with customer request and utilization of skills in opposition to the accumulation and possession of it. Therefore, it can be seen that performance of organizations is as the result of the strategies and its operational methods and it is the level at which it achieves its set goals.

The performance of an institution is gauged not just on financial aspects which include returns on accounts, market stock and measures of growth but the non-financial aspects that include orientation of clients, personal satisfaction and social performance (Combs, Crook & Shook, 2015). According to Richard, Devinney, Yip and Johnson (2016) institutional performance are about measuring the real productivity of the firm within which is linked to an more effective and efficient methods and also the external measures that involves corporate social responsibility that is related to considering a broad view other than the value of the economy.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Organizations are open systems that are vulnerable to the internal processes since they contribute to the general performance either directly or indirectly. Over the past years in Kenya, there has been significant growth in public healthcare institutions. This is perceived to result from changes in their operations and internal processes. In this manner, multiple public healthcare institutions radically alter how they operate and relate to such a dynamic environment (Marmouse, 2017). Kimathi (2018) highlights that change management's main aim is to maximize benefits and achieve organizational objectives with minimal risks involved in the change implementation process. Inadequacies in the healthcare systems in Kenya have been a barrier to implementing internal change management processes; however, healthcare in Kenya is under a devolved government.

The unsuitable social and economic conditions have significantly impacted delivering effective healthcare services across the country. Lack of implementation of internal change management processes such as employee training and developing suitable organizational structure has affected service delivery in healthcare institutions, as observed by Oyuga (2018). Choge (2020) observed that Kakamega County General Teaching and Referral Hospital is faced with the challenges of providing quality health care. The challenges are contributed by a shortage of medical staff with specialized skills, and unconducive work environment, inappropriate organizational structure, and inadequate computerized systems across all departments. In essence, the doctor population ratio stands at 1:34,916 patients, and that for the nurses is, while the nurse-patient ratio is one nurse to 2,658 patients. These challenges call for improved performance to be achieved by implementing internal change management processes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Human Capital Theory (HCT), which Schultz created in the year 1961, proposes that value creation by members of an organization is of help in improving employee performance. According to human capital theory, people are non-costs assets within a business entity. The human resource within an organization is an indication of human capital, which is the sum of intelligence, skills, and expertise that gives the organization its particular personality. However, this can only be obtained through employee training which further contributes to increased performance. The HCT highlights the value that individuals may provide to a company. This is referred to as a condition that confers a "human capital advantage" by Briam (2016). Because human capital is an intangible asset, the company that employs it does not own it. However much there is lack of legal ownership of human capital, organizations often receive benefits from organizations whenever staffs are highly trained through creation of corporate cultures or learning vocabulary phrases to foster cohesion.

According to James (2018), The Human Capital Theory lays emphasis on the significance of training the employees to achieve institutional performance. Staff training contributes towards improved knowledge, skills and empowerment that

further translates to improved institutional performance. This theory is therefore relevant for the study as it significant to the study since human capital is a critical component in enhancing an organization's assets. As a result, an organization's internal human resource management must be effective in finding and keeping the most qualified and efficient employees to boost productivity and compete effectively in the global marketplace. The notion is based on the assumption that staff training and development are critical to improving employee productivity and organizational performance.

Empirical Literature Review

Implementation of relevant training practices within an organization contributes towards development of particular skills and abilities by the staffs, hence enhancing institutional performance (Cummings, 2016). Trainings enables different organizations to determine the initial level of performance of the staff members, from which areas of weaknesses and strengths can be achieved. Therefore, modeling of the knowledge and skills can be realized among the staffs through relevant training processes. Johnson (2018) points out that the training processes need to be frequently done to enable the employees possess certain skills and knowledge for performing different tasks.

There are multiple studies that have been carried out to determine the relationship between employee training and institutional performance. Cania et al., (2016) conducted a study to determine the effects of employees training on the organization's performance in Albania. The study made use of longitudinal research study design and stratified random sampling. The data collection was conducted through questionnaires, conducted in three different cities in Albania. Data analysis or the study was in three major phases. The initial phase involved reliability and factorial analysis whereas the second phase involved multicollinearity tests. The last phase of data analysis entailed hypothesis testing of the study questions by the use of multiple regression and Analysis of Variance. The study findings indicate that there is a positive correlation between employee's training the organizational performance. The study also determined that training of the employees may however not be the only variable influencing the performance presenting a theoretical gap. This study did not however assess other variables affecting institutional performance during change management such as organizational structure and adoption of the information and communications technology.

In Kenya, Gitongu (2020) conducted a study to assess the influence of employee training on the performance of Three-Star Rated Hotels in Nakuru County. The study made use of descriptive research study design and stratified random sampling from which a sample size of 357 respondents selected was selected by the study out of a target population of 5111 employees. Questionnaires were used to achieve collection of data. Analysis of the determined data was though descriptive and inferential statistics. The study findings determined that the more the employees acquire new skills, and knowledge, they become highly productive hence promoting organizational performance. This study did not however assess other variables affecting institutional performance during change management such as organizational structure and adoption of the information and communications technology.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study made use of descriptive research design. The study took place in Kakamega County General Teaching and Referral Hospital and the respondents were made up of 551 employees from the 5 departments of the hospital namely; accidents and emergency, infection prevention and control, marketing and communication, nutrition, nursing and mental health. The sampling design to be used by the study was stratified sampling from which respondents were grouped into various strata in ensuring all the respondents are adequately represented. Respondents were selected using simple random sampling method was used to select the respondents. Study sample size constituted 232 respondents as determined by the study. Ten random respondents from the hospital were considered to be part of the pilot study. The researcher was required to brief the management on the purpose of the research study prior to data collection. At this point, the researcher assured the management, and all the respondents within the hospital of confidentiality as no individual would be victimized based on the response provided. The researcher administered the questionnaires by herself through drop and pick. Quantitative data achieved by the survey was presented in the form of mean averages, frequencies, and percentages. Besides, Statistical Packages for Social Sciences., version 25 was also incorporated into the data analysis. Analysis of the qualitative data was done through content analysis. This method was helpful in coming up with the study inferences. Study findings were also presented in the form of percentages and tables

4. FINDINGS

The descriptive results of employee training are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Employee Training

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employee tutoring empowers knowledge gain as well as enhancement of the relevant skills that makes them more productive, hence increases performance level.	4.00	1.202
Employee training empowers the employees, thereby making them highly contribute towards the performance of Kakamega general Country referral Hospital	4.07	0.835
Corporate institutional training of employees enables them acquire skills on innovation that improves their capabilities and individual performances	4.51	0.583
Employee Training will be useful to the human resource management of Kakamega general Country referral Hospital in determining the performance levels of individual employees	4.15	0.833
Employee Training contributes towards institutional performance by preparing the employees to uptake higher roles within the hospital	4.61	0.610

The results as presented in Table 4.4 shows that the respondents strong agreed on the statements that employee Training contributes towards institutional performance by preparing the employees to uptake higher roles within the hospital and that corporate institutional training of employees enables them acquire skills on innovation that improves their capabilities and individual performances with a mean of 4.61 and 4.51 respectively. These statements had a low variation of response as indicated by standard deviation of 0.610 and 0.583 respectively.

The respondents agreed on the statements that employee Training will be useful to the human resource management of Kakamega general Country referral Hospital in determining the performance levels of individual employees, employee training empowers the employees, thereby making them highly contribute towards the performance of Kakamega general Country referral Hospital and that employee tutoring empowers knowledge gain as well as enhancement of the relevant skills that makes them more productive, hence increases performance level as with a mean of 4.15, 4.07 and 4.00 respectively. These statements had a low variation of response as indicated by standard deviation of 0.833, 0.835 and 1.202 respectively.

Results of Regression Analysis

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.751 ^a	.823	.808	.796

From the findings in Table 2 the value of adjusted r squared was 0.808(80.8%) an indication that there was variation of 80.8% of the institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital attributed to employee training. Additionally, this therefore means that factors not studied in this research contribute 19.2% of the institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F.	Sig.
1	Regression	19.723	1	19.723	31.51	.000
	Residual	140.135	224	0.626		
	Total	159.858	225			

The results in Table 3 show that significance value obtained was .000 which was less than 0.05. In addition, the F statistics computed at a 5% level of relevance was 31.51 with a p-value of 0.000 which was above statistical mean square value at 19.723. This shows that the model could be used for further statistical analysis.

Table 4: Coefficient

		Unstandardised coefficients		Unstandardised coefficients		
		B	Sd.Err	Beta	t	Sig.
Model	(Constant)	1.779	.360		4.942	.000
1	Employee training	.744	.070	.143	10.629	.001

From the above regression model, holding employee training constant, institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital, would be 1.779. The regression coefficient of employee training was 0.744 showing the extent to which institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital would increase by increasing a single unit in employee training. In addition employee training contributed to a positive significant influence to institutional performance in Kakamega County Referral Hospital as indicated by t-value at 10.629 with a significance level less than 0.05 at 0.001

Institutional performance = 1.779 + 0.744 employee training

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that training improves performance by lowering employee turnover and raising commitment to organizational goals and objectives. For the organizations, training the staff was essential to ensuring their smooth comprehension of the work, skill development, and readiness to perform effectively. The in-service workforce and newly hired employees of an organization both required training.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that the hospital should conduct a training needs assessment in order to establish a fundamental and distinct business goal for the training supports. SWOT analysis should be used to determine skill gaps. Create a learning objective that takes the knowledge, skills, or attitude into consideration. Create training materials that are centered on the employees' needs for learning and that directly relate to the learning goals. The hospital should be aware of its requirements and execute training accordingly, creating an engaging environment to maintain interest throughout the entire procedure.

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